

THE DEVELOPMENT OF BEHAVIOR PROBLEMS AMONG DISABLED ANDNON- DISABLED CHILDREN IN ENGLAND

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Annotation: This study identifies the incidence and development of disabled children's problem behaviors during the early years. Using the Millennium Cohort Study, a nationally representative UK study, and a measure of disability anchored in the UK legal definition, we estimate growth curve models tracking behavior problems from ages 3 to 7.

Key words: England, Disability, Behavior problems, Early years, Trajectories, Millennium Cohort Study.

Introduction background: The emergence of problem behavior during the early years may set children upon unfavorable developmental trajectories. This is particularly true in the case of early externalizing behavior problems which may lead to continued problems and poor academic achievement . Boys and girls tend to exhibit problem behavior differently, with higher rates of externalizing problems documented for boys and, to some extent, more internalizing problems for girls. Past research has shown that disabled children are more likely than their non-disabled peers to present behavior problems, including social and peer problems, conduct problems and oppositional behaviors, attention difficulties and hyperactivity, and internalizing problems, and that their problems are more likely to be within the clinical range relative to their peers. Yet, we know little about the extent to which associations between disability and behavior are linked to children's developmental stage and whether they attenuate or intensify around the time of school entry. We know from decades of research the critical nature of the early years, in which both genes and the environment—and the interplay between the two—set into motion the development of brain structures that affect children for the rest of their lives. More

proximally, children's development up to age 3 provides the building blocks for the increasingly complex social behaviors, emotional maturity, problem solving ability, and early literacy and numeracy skills that are critical leading up to school entry. For some children, early behavioral problems are temporary, resolved over the normal course of development, while for others they persist or even intensify in the early school years. School entry represents an expansion in children's developmental ecology from the primacy of parents and the home environment to incorporate the school context and peers. Whether disabled children's behavioral development tracks that of their non-disabled peers over the first few years following this transition to school is an important empirical endeavor, a better understanding of which will help to inform the timing of interventions for disabled children. A description of disabled children's early behavioral trajectories across four important domains of behavioral development is the first contribution of this paper. Using longitudinal data from the UK Millennium Cohort Study (MCS), a large, nationally representative sample of children born in 2000–2001, we examine four problem behaviors: conduct problems, hyperactivity, peer problems, and emotional symptoms. These distinct types of problem behavior have been shown to be important for children's development, and they may present differently over time for disabled and non-disabled children. We address the question of whether young disabled children growing up in England experience more behavioral problems, and in which domains, than their non-disabled counterparts at age 3, and if any initial gap in behavior widens between the ages of 3 and 7. Finally, we examine whether differences in behavioral trajectories are contingent on three aspects of parenting and the home environment. Given the importance of the family and home environment for young children's behavioral development, supportive and enriching experiences in the home could help mitigate the development of behavior problems for young disabled children. On the other hand, given increased levels of parenting stress associated with parenting a young disabled child, it may be that less favorable family climates exacerbate differences in behavior problems between disabled and non-disabled children. To our knowledge, despite the wealth of research attesting to the importance of home environment on

children's development, and the ways in which it can mitigate socio-economic disadvantage , research has not examined whether family environments promote greater convergence or divergence of behavioral trajectories between disabled and non-disabled children over time. The paper's third contribution is to investigate the moderating role of parental warmth and harshness and the home learning environment on disabled children's behavioral trajectories; notably to better understand which aspects of parenting and the home environment attenuate or exacerbate which problem behaviors.

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